

SPECIAL PREVENTION OF OFFENSES CARRIED OUT BY THE CRIME PREVENTION SERVICES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract

The article discusses the activities of special prevention of offenses carried out by the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies, and offers proposals and recommendations for the more effective organization of this activity.

Key words: internal affairs bodies, crime prevention services, offenses, special prevention of offenses, measures.

In our country, the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies play a crucial role in ensuring the protection of individuals' rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, raising legal awareness and legal culture in society, strengthening the rule of law, as well as identifying, studying, and implementing measures to eliminate the causes and conditions contributing to the commission of offenses. They are also important in the social rehabilitation and adaptation of victims of offenses, individuals prone to committing offenses, those who have committed offenses, including previously convicted persons and those released from places of detention, and in reducing the risk of individuals becoming victims of offenses - in other words, in carrying out crime prevention.

In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention"[1] outlines the system of bodies and institutions that carry out and participate in crime prevention, their powers, and identifies the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan as one of the bodies carrying out this activity. Within the system of internal affairs bodies, the main and wide-ranging structure for crime prevention is the Crime Prevention Services of the Public Security Department. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention"[2], one of the types of crime prevention they carry out is special prevention of offenses.

Special prevention of offenses is the activity of bodies and institutions directly engaged in crime prevention, involving the development and implementation of special measures aimed at preventing certain types of offenses, eliminating the causes and conditions that contribute to their commission, identifying certain categories of persons, and exerting preventive influence on them.

It should be noted that the increase in certain types of offenses, the number of categories of individuals at risk, and the emergence of threats and risks that encroach on public order and public safety, as well as the interests of individuals, society, and the state, form the basis for implementing special prevention of offenses. In carrying out this activity, the crime prevention services of the internal affairs bodies play a crucial role.

One of the characteristics of special crime prevention is that it consists only of special measures that are carried out on the initiative and under the guidance of subjects directly carrying out crime prevention, based on pre-developed and approved by internal order

special plans. In particular, the crime prevention services of the internal affairs bodies, in order to constantly effectively organize and implement special crime prevention among previously convicted persons, persons who abuse alcohol or use narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and other substances affecting the intellectual and volitional activity, as well as minors, develop and implement special preventive plans based on these plans (for example, against the illegal trafficking of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and other substances affecting the intellectual and volitional activity - "Antiterrorist"; for the prevention of In other words, special crime prevention differs from other types of prevention in that it is often directed towards areas with a serious crime situation and individuals prone to committing crimes, as well as is carried out on the basis of special instructions and assignments.

In the development and implementation of special crime prevention, timely organization and coordination of the activities of crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies, constant monitoring, analysis, and planning of this activity are of great importance.

At the same time, it is advisable to develop the specifics of the territory and period in which special crime prevention measures are carried out, the essence of the factors that cause and contribute to the commission of crimes, the personality of the perpetrators of crimes, the strengths and capabilities of the internal affairs bodies in preventing these types of crimes. In other words, for the effective implementation of special crime prevention measures on the spot or on time, qualitatively and for the future, all structural structures should reflect in their monthly, quarterly and annual reports what types of offenses or categories of individuals are increasing in their respective territories, as well as negative situations that encroach on public order and public safety, the interests of the individual, society, and the state, and in their plans for their future activities, determine and implement measures to prevent them, which will have a positive impact not only on the state of offenses in the territories assign

It can be said that the crime prevention services of the internal affairs bodies should carry out special crime prevention activities in two directions:

Special criminological prevention of offenses is a special prevention aimed at reducing the category of individuals with antisocial behavior and lifestyle who have committed or are prone to committing offenses.

2. Special victimological prevention of offenses - that is, special prevention aimed at reducing the category of victims of committed offenses and individuals with a high probability of becoming victims of potential future offenses.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses," measures aimed at developing and implementing special measures aimed at preventing certain types of offenses, eliminating the causes and conditions conducive to the commission of these types of offenses, identifying certain categories of individuals and providing them with preventive assistance are organized in the following areas:

- special prevention of offenses among previously convicted persons;
- special prevention of offenses among persons addicted to alcohol, who use narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and other substances that affect the intellectual and volitional activity;
- special prevention of neglect and delinquency among minors.

Special prevention of offenses among previously convicted persons is one of the main areas of activity of preventive services.[4] Despite the fact that significant work is being done in our country to prevent offenses among previously convicted individuals, the conducted

studies show that there is still much work to be done in this area. In particular, if we turn to statistical data, in the first nine months of 2024, due to insufficient preventive measures against previously convicted persons, 4,903 crimes were committed by this category of persons, 1,113 by previously convicted persons, 638 by persons under administrative supervision, including 20 by highly dangerous recidivists. Of the 36,245 individuals who committed the crimes, 4,011 were previously convicted.[5] These circumstances demonstrate the importance of preventing offenses among previously convicted individuals.

M.Z. Ziyodullaev emphasizes that when implementing crime prevention among previously convicted individuals, prevention inspectors primarily focus on conducting preventive work with individuals under the administrative supervision of internal affairs bodies, previously convicted individuals who do not fall under the influence of administrative supervision, as well as individuals who have been sentenced to non-custodial sentences and who have been conditionally convicted. Indeed, preventive work with these categories is of great importance today.

To eliminate problematic situations in this area, it is necessary to increase the responsibility of social adaptation centers under local khokimiyats in systematically organizing vocational training for persons serving sentences or the process of their vocational training and providing employment for persons released from penitentiary institutions. At the same time, it is advisable to widely cooperate with civil society institutions in addressing the socio-domestic problems of individuals released from penal institutions and to further expand the practice of encouraging civil society institutions that provide close assistance in these processes.

Crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies also play an important role in the implementation of special crime prevention measures among individuals who abuse alcohol or use narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and other substances that affect intellectual and volitional activity, and this direction requires special responsibility from industry employees.

Criminologists assess chronic alcoholism and drug addiction as one of the specific anomalies, noting that in most cases they lead to the commission of offenses and that such individuals are prone to committing crimes.[7] According to A.B. Kulakhmedov, drug addiction and drug aggression have a social risk and a growth rate in numbers and are equally characteristic of all countries.[8]

It can be said that today in our country, significant work is being carried out on special prevention of offenses among this category of individuals. However, the studies conducted in this direction show that there is still much work to be done. Specifically, the fact that crimes committed while intoxicated amounted to 1,841 in our republic in 10 months of 2024 shows how important it is for law enforcement agencies to constantly implement appropriate preventive measures with this category of individuals. In particular, in this direction, as R.A. Semenyuk noted, it is of particular importance that they constantly cooperate with drug doctors and other specialists of medical institutions in this process. It is also advisable to carry out the following work in this direction:

first, to prevent an increase in this category of people in the relevant regions, strengthen special preventive measures, that is, regularly monitor the activities of stores specializing in the sale of alcoholic beverages, as well as pharmacies;

secondly, further strengthening of special preventive measures to return this category of persons to a normal lifestyle, that is, first of all, revision of regulatory legal acts regulating activities in this area. For example, simplifying the procedure for sending a person for mandatory medical treatment and creating adequate medical conditions for their treatment.

It is necessary to define the activities of the crime prevention services of the internal affairs bodies in the prevention of neglect and crime among minors as a separate direction in the field of crime prevention. The reason is that the prevention of neglect and delinquency among minors also requires the implementation of general, individual, and victimological preventive measures according to their content.[11] In particular, at the IV congress of the youth movement, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "Our most important direction is youth. If we solve this issue, we will achieve great changes." [12] In particular, today in our country, large-scale positive reforms are being carried out to ensure the rights and legitimate interests of minors. For example, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Further Improve Socio-Legal Assistance to Minors" introduced a completely new system for providing socio-legal assistance to minors. Based on this system, a clear procedure for working with minors in need of state and public assistance has been established, and how to work with children has been shown. However, despite the positive reforms being implemented, the number of offenses committed by minors has not significantly decreased. For example, the fact that 2215 crimes were committed by minors in 10 months of 2024 shows the need for systematic work to further strengthen educational work in educational institutions and local self-government bodies to prevent offenses among them, increase the responsibility of parents for raising their children, and meaningfully organize their free time.

Indeed, timely identification and work with minors who have been left unattended and abandoned, identification of minors who commit offenses, persons who involve them in crime and other anti-social activities, and conducting appropriate preventive work, as well as preventing organized crime among minors, are priorities in this area.[15]

Furthermore, when implementing crime prevention among minors, it is necessary to consider the specifics of their personality and those around them, the degree of their social danger, the conditions of their upbringing in the family, and the nature of the offense or antisocial behavior committed.[16]. At the same time, individual prevention of juvenile delinquency involves measures aimed at identifying minors in socially dangerous situations, socio-pedagogical rehabilitation, and preventing the commission of offenses or other antisocial behavior.[17]

In order to effectively organize crime prevention and prevent offenses among minors, who are the future of our society, it is advisable to improve the system of work with minors based on the principle of "seven neighboring parents to one child," as indicated in our local traditions, in cooperation with interested ministries and agencies, as well as civil society institutions, whose role in our society is increasing every day. At the same time, it is necessary to organize effective work in the self-government bodies of citizens with parents who have not properly fulfilling their obligations to educate and educate their children, and to establish the practice of discussing parents who have committed irresponsibility in mahallas.

It is also advisable to protect minors from the antisocial behavior and influence of their parents, their substitutes, and other adults, identify parents, their substitutes, and other

persons involved in offenses, the use of alcohol and drugs, begging, as well as families in socially dangerous situations, organize preventive work with them, and in this regard, it is advisable to pay special attention to the interaction of crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies with civil society institutions. In particular, fostering in minors a sense of patriotism, civic duty, tolerance, respect for laws, national and universal values, resistance to harmful influences, various trends, firm beliefs and views on life, and their protection from actions that violate moral foundations, terrorism and extremism, separatism, fundamentalism, violence and cruelty, raising the legal awareness and legal culture of young people, implementing crime prevention among young people, as well as establishing a wide range of cooperation between crime prevention services and civil society institutions in identifying the

In conclusion, it can be said that when organizing special crime prevention, it is advisable to adopt a regulatory legal act defining the mechanisms for developing special and operational preventive measures aimed at eliminating the causes and conditions contributing to their commission, identifying certain categories of individuals and exerting preventive influence on them. This document should clearly define the grounds, subjects, timelines, forces and means involved, material and technical support, and appropriate procedures and rules for the development and conduct of such special events. After all, the lack of development of specific mechanisms for implementing the norms in the adopted laws, the absence of relevant subordinate legal acts that contribute to the effective functioning of laws, often leads to the failure of these laws.

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